

DESIGN OF EXPERIMENTS ANALYSIS OF THE ON-LINE CONSOLIDATION PROCESS

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SUMMARY: An on-line consolidation system, which includes a computer-controlled filament winding machine and a consolidation head assembly, has been designed and constructed to fabricate composite parts from thermoplastic towpregs. The present study examines the impact of processing conditions on thickness reduction, void content, density, degree of crystallinity, and interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of the consolidated parts. A central composite experimental design was used to select the processing conditions for manufacturing the composite cylinders and to analyze the effect of processing parameters on quality of resulting composite cylinders. A response surface of ILSS was constructed to reveal the impact of the individual parameters. In general, higher nippoint temperature and lower winding speed tend to yield composite cylinders with higher ILSS and lower void content. APC-2 (PEEK/Carbon fiber) composite cylinders fabricated by the on-line consolidation technique had an ILSS of 58 MPa and less than 1% void content.

KEYWORDS: On-line (In-situ) consolidation, thermoplastic composites, design of experiments, interlaminar shear strength, APC-2 towpreg, void content, degree of crystallinity.

INTRODUCTION

On-line consolidation is a composite manufacturing process where the resin impregnated fiber bundles (“towpreg” or “prepreg”) are continuously oriented, laid down, consolidated, and cured onto the tool surface in a single step. Once the surface of the designed structure has been covered and the thickness has been achieved, the part is finished. Secondary processing steps such as autoclave or hot-press consolidation are eliminated. When integrated with a computer controlled system, the process can be fully automated which leads to further cost saving in fabrication by increasing productivity and reducing labor cost.

In addition to the reduced cost, on-line consolidation also offers benefits for design flexibility and performance. With localized heating, this process is inherently suitable for manufacturing parts with large surfaces and moderate curvatures, such as fuselage structures and deep submersibles [1]. Because the towpreg is fully consolidated and locked in the vicinity of the melting point as it is placed onto the structure, conceptually there is no limitation on producing parts with thick cross-sections and large surface areas [2]. Furthermore, complex, non-geodesic, and even concave winding paths are also achievable, thus allowing design flexibility [3].

In order to realize the potential advantages of on-line consolidation, the significant processing parameters must be identified and the effects of the processing parameters on the quality of the composite must be understood.

Therefore, the objectives of this investigation are to use a design of experiments approach to determine the importance of the processing parameters and their effect on the mechanical and physical properties of the consolidated composite.

EXPERIMENTAL

On-Line Consolidation System

Over the past decade, many investigations have been devoted to development of the on-line consolidation manufacturing technique [4-12]. Almost all existing on-line consolidation systems have similar processing steps that start with unwinding prepreg from the spool. The continuous towpreg passes through a tensioner and guide rollers and then arrives at the nip point, where the towpreg and composite substrate meet. Energy from a highly focused heat source melts the interface while, at the same time, the compacting roller compresses the material and squeezes out excess resin. Finally, the towpreg is solidified and consolidated onto the tool surface.

The on-line consolidation system used in the present investigation is schematically illustrated in Figure 1 and includes a towpreg delivery system, a computer-controlled filament winding machine and a consolidation head assembly. Figure 2 shows a photograph of the on-line consolidation system.

The on-line consolidation system, described above, was used to manufacture composite cylinders from 6.35 mm wide APC-2 towpreg (carbon fiber and PEEK) from Fiberite, Inc. The winding pattern was generated by the computer software, CADWIND®. The winding procedure was performed on a computer controlled two-axis filament winding machine. All cylinders investigated are hoop-wound and have an inner diameter of 146 mm (5.75 in).

Figure 1 Illustration of the on-line consolidation system.

Figure 2 Photograph of the on-line consolidation system.

Mechanical and Physical Tests

Once a composite cylinder was produced, its thickness was measured and recorded at twenty different locations around the circumference. The composite cylinders were then sent to the machine shop for fabricating test coupons. First, a 6.35 mm wide ring was cut out from the center portion of the cylinder. Second, a thin diamond cutter was used to cut open the ring and the opening dimension was then recorded. Different displacements indicate that the process-induced residual stresses have varied due to different processing conditions. Third, fifteen ILSS coupons were machined to conform to the dimensional requirements as described in ASTM standard D2344.

To gage the overall quality, density and void content tests were performed on all composite cylinders. The density measurements were performed in accordance with ASTM standard D792-91 and the void content measurements were performed in accordance with ASTM standard D2734-91. The material densities required by the void content calculation are given in Table 1. The density of APC-2 at 30% crystallinity was determined following the procedures described in Ref. 13.

Table 1 Material Properties for Density Calculation.

Property	AS-4 Fiber	PEEK	
		Amorphous	Crystallinity
Volume Fraction	60%	40%	
Degree of Crystallinity	na	na	30%
Density (kg/m ³)	1780.0	1262.6	1400.6

STATISTICAL INVESTIGATION OF THE PROCESSING WINDOW

The motivation for using a statistical method was to study the impact of individual processing parameters and to establish the processing window for a given material system. In contrast to randomly selected processing conditions or to conducting one-factor-at-a-time studies, a carefully planned experimental design for studying the impact of all variables and their interactions will be more cost-effective.

Processing Parameters

In the present design, there are five separately controllable system parameters namely, winding speed, pressure of compaction roller, nozzle temperature, distance between nozzle and nip point, and air pressure for the heater.

Observations from initial experiments showed that the nip point temperature can be several hundred degrees Celsius lower than the nozzle temperature and is very sensitive to the following three system parameters: nozzle temperature, air flow rate in heater and distance between nip point and nozzle. Meanwhile, we found that using nip point temperature to construct the processing window has two major advantages. First, it is more realistic since nip point temperature is the actual temperature that the towpregs are subjected to. Second, by using nip point temperature to represent three of the system parameters, the number of

parameters was reduced from five down to three, i.e. winding speed, roller pressure, and actual nippoint temperature.

Nippoint Temperature

In order to investigate the individual impact of these three parameters and their interaction on the nippoint temperature, a three-factor, Box-Behnken design was conducted [14]. There are fifteen possible factor-level combinations in this experimental design. The low, midpoint, and high values are listed as the following.

- Distance between nozzle to nippoint: 12.7 mm (0.5 in), 19.1 mm (0.75 in) and 25.4 mm (1.0 in).
- Air pressure: 27.6 kPa (4 psi), 55.2 kPa (8 psi) and 82.7 kPa (12 psi).
- Nozzle temperature of hot air heater : 538°C (1000°F), 593°C (1100°F) and 649°C (1200°F).

The nippoint temperature was measured by a K-type, air-probe thermocouple for each factor-level combination. A second-order linear regression analysis for three independent variables yields,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Nippoint Temperature} (^{\circ}\text{C}) = & \\ & 138.14 + 26.682 D - 1.151 P - 0.3427 T - 0.209 D^2 \\ & - 0.002 P^2 + 0.0017 T^2 + 0.002 DP - 0.0417 TD + 0.0016 PT \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where D is the distance from nozzle to nippoint, P is the heater air pressure, and T is nozzle temperature.

Processing Window For On-Line Consolidation System

The processing window for the on-line consolidation system is determined by adjusting the three system processing parameters, namely roller pressure, winding speed, and nippoint temperature. To simplify the approach a step further, a fixed roller pressure of 380 kPa (55 psi) was chosen for fabricating all cylinders. It should be noted that we are not presuming that there is no significant impact of pressure on the quality of composite cylinders; a fixed roller pressure is simply a system constraint for the present design. For now, the study is focused on the impact of winding speed and nippoint temperature on composite quality.

First, a two-factor central composite design of experiments was used to define the combination of processing parameters. Second, the density and the thickness of the resulting cylinders were measured and then, as described in the previous section, their void content was calculated. Micrographs of the cross sections of each consolidated part are used to qualitatively describe the consolidation for a set of processing conditions. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to measure the degree of crystallinity. Finally, the interlaminar shear strength of consolidated parts was measured.

Central Composite Design

A central composite design of experiments was used to systematically study the processing window and to maximize the quality of composite parts. An illustration of the two-factor central composite design is given in Figure 3. The levels for winding speed range from about 4-10 mm/s and the nippoint temperature has a high value of 660°C (1220°F) and a low value of 493°C (920°F). Nine composite cylinders, 26-ply thick and 19 mm (3/4 in) wide were

fabricated under the prescribed processing conditions given by the experimental design. The winding time ranges from 77 to 172 minutes.

Figure 3 Illustration of a two-factor central composite design.

Micrograph Study on Quality of Consolidated Cylinders

The purpose of the optical micrographs taken at cross sections of each composite cylinder is three-fold. First, we can visually observe the degree of intimate contact between layers since intimate contact is the necessary condition for good bonding. Second, we can examine whether or not the fiber distribution is uniform. Third, we can observe the size and location of voids, for void content reflects composite quality. As a result, the micrographs give a qualitative description of the composite quality.

Specimens were cut from each composite cylinder and mounted in an epoxy potting compound. Each cross section was carefully polished and analyzed under an optical microscope. Figure 4 shows results for cylinders #2 and #8. Cylinder #2 was manufactured under a nippoint temperature of 633°C (1172°F) and a winding speed of 3.71 mm/s (8.76 in/min.), and the micrographs are shown in Figures 4(a)-4(c). Virtually no voids are observed at the interply region (Figure 4(a)) and the fiber distribution is uniform (Figure 4(b)). No significant fiber waviness confirms that on-line consolidation does have an advantage over conventional autoclave consolidation where fiber waviness usually occurs (Figure 4(c)).

As expected, not all cylinders yield the same high quality. In the case of cylinder #8, manufactured under a nippoint temperature of 517°C and a winding speed of 7.91 mm/s, large, resin-rich areas exist at almost every interply region as shown in Figure 4(d). Under external loading, the resin-rich areas are the most vulnerable due to the lack of surrounding reinforcement. This observation suggests that the specimens from cylinder #8 may fail much

more easily than the specimens cut from a well-consolidated cylinder in which the fibers are distributed more uniformly.

Figure 4 Photo micrographs of cross-section of Cylinders #2 and #8.

Table 2: Properties of towpreg and consolidated APC-2 cylinders.

Cylinder Number	Nippoint Temp. °C	Processing Speed mm/s	Density kg/m ³ (std. dev.)	Void % (std. dev.)	Thickness mm (std. dev.)	ILSS Mpa (std. dev.)	Degree of Crystallinity%
APC-2	na	na	1470.1 (6.0)	7.3 (0.8)	na	na	15.1
1	572	6.34	1543.5 (3.4)	2.9 (0.2)	3.20 (0.03)	45.20 (0.66)	32.8
2	633	3.71	1584.2 (6.3)	0.4 (0.3)	2.91 (0.04)	58.4 (1.49)	29.4
3	572	9.97	1523.3 (2.9)	4.2 (0.2)	3.47 (0.02)	33.44 (1.50)	29.0
4	572	5.53	1563.4 (3.3)	1.7 (0.2)	3.18 (0.07)	52.38 (1.90)	32.7
5	517	3.71	1544.5 (3.0)	2.8 (0.2)	3.25 (0.02)	49.00 (0.82)	33.6
6	662	6.34	1565.6 (3.6)	1.5 (0.2)	3.06 (0.03)	54.67 (1.26)	29.2
7	496	6.34	1514.6 (13.8)	4.7 (0.9)	3.58 (0.02)	30.74 (1.74)	30.4
8	517	7.91	1516.0 (4.0)	4.6 (0.2)	3.60 (0.02)	24.74 (1.20)	26.5
9	633	7.91	1545.6 (3.6)	2.8 (0.2)	3.26 (0.02)	46.26 (0.84)	27.4

Effect of Processing Parameters on Interlaminar Shear Strength

After investigating the impact of processing parameters on the density, void content and degree of crystallinity, the next logical step was to conduct interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) tests that give a quantitative description of the bonding quality of the resulting cylinders. Table 2 shows the density, void content, degree of crystallinity and ILSS for all consolidated cylinders. For an APC-2 composite, an interlaminar shear strength of 72 MPa (10.4 ksi) has been reported by

using the manufacturer's recommended processing conditions, i.e. 380°C for 5 minutes under a hot press loading at 1380 kPa (200 psi) [7]. The average ILSS obtained from cylinder #2 is about 80% of the ILSS of flat compression molded composite laminates. Therefore, we consider the present design of the on-line consolidation system an acceptable one.

In order to study how ILSS varies under various settings of processing conditions, a response surface using a two-factor central composite design was constructed. A second order linear regression model can be written as follows:

$$ILSS = -14.9207 + 0.31192 NT - 19.663 WS \\ - 0.000278 NT^2 + 0.1643 WS^2 + 0.0244 NT \times WS \quad (2)$$

where:

ILSS = interlaminar shear strength, MPa,

NT = nippoint temperature, °C,

WS = winding speed, mm/s.

Figure 5 shows the impact of nippoint temperature and winding speed on the interlaminar shear strength of consolidated composite cylinders. In general, higher nippoint temperature and lower winding speed yield higher ILSS. For convenience, a contour plot of the response surface is given in Figure 6. If the highest strength is desired, we can wind the cylinder at a lower speed and a higher temperature. However, if productivity is a concern, winding the cylinder at a higher speed and at a higher nippoint temperature will not sacrifice too much strength. It should be noted that all observations made here are good only for the range investigated for each variable and cannot be used to explicitly study the ILSS response outside this range.

CONCLUSIONS

A statistical approach was used to determine the significant processing parameters and their effect on the mechanical and physical properties of composite cylinders fabricated by on-line consolidation of thermoplastic towpreg. A central composite experimental design was used to select the processing conditions for manufacturing the composite cylinders. The thickness, density, void content, degree of crystallinity and interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) were measured for each composite cylinder. A second order linear regression analysis was used to construct a response surface relating nippoint temperature and winding speed to interlaminar shear strength (ILSS). Results of the analysis give the proper combinations of nippoint temperature and winding speed that will result in well consolidated composite cylinders. Under optimal processing conditions, an ILSS of 58 MPa and a void content of <1% were achieved with APC-2 towpreg.

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Figure 5 Impact of nippoint temperature and winding speed on the interlaminar shear strength.

Figure 6 Contours of constant ILSS, in MPa.

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